

Micro-turbines for energy recovery in WWTP

Deliverable 2.3

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Summary

Deliverable 2.3 is a technical report on the work carried out in Task 2.1 within the Alicante Living Lab, more specifically in subtask 2.1.2 that had the objective of developing, customizing and demonstrating a pilot scale microturbine for energy recovery from WWTP effluents.

A pico turbine was installed at the outflow of the Monte Orgegia WWTP in Alicante as a demonstrator for energy recuperation at any kind of business processing large amounts of water. The demonstrator showed that regardless of the size of the turbine, a roughly similar level of efficiency can be delivered. Nevertheless, if a water-treatment site has been setup with energy-efficiency in mind, the energy-recuperation capability could be low. The business case for pico turbines is more in the direction of businesses with low-power needs, close to rivers or irrigation channels.

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Lead beneficiary	Milestone author(s)
TURB	Luc Berben Ignacio Casals (AMAEM), Mariano García (AMAEM), Aida Poveda (AMAEM)
Quality assurance	
Eric Santos (CETAQUA)	
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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AMAEM Aguas de Alicante

CFD Computational Fluid Dynamics

CHP Combined Heat and Power

CMS Cubic meter per second (m³/s)

EC European Commission

EU European Union

LCOE Levelized cost of electricity

LL Living Lab

M Month

PE Population Equivalent

PRV Pressure-reducing valves

WP Work Package

WWTP Wastewater Treatment Plant

V_{bat} battery voltage

Revision history

Feedback received	How the feedback has been integrated in D2.3
<p>Could you please discuss the economic and environmental viability of the featured technology beyond the brief discussion in the conclusions section.</p>	<p>A new section has been included “5. Impact, market and conditions” extending the discussion of the economic and environmental viability of microturbines.</p>
<p>This needs to answer the question about the potential return on investment and other operational and economic aspects for this type of energy recovery.</p>	<p>In this new section 5. Impact, market and conditions the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) has been estimated and discussed.</p>
<p>Compared to the typical energy demand of WWTPs, the produced amount (about 1.5 kW/h) appears to be not of high significance, probably below 0.5 % of the total energy demand of the studied WWTP. Please elaborate on this aspect and put the technology in the broader context (viability of micro-turbines vs. PV, biogas, etc.)</p>	<p>The new section compares in terms of economic and environmental impact the use of turbines with solar and wind energies.</p>

Executive summary

D2.3 represents a comprehensive technical report that integrates the efforts conducted within the scope of subtask 2.1.2, focusing on the energy recovery from water effluents in Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTP) in the Living Lab of Alicante.

A picoturbine was installed at the outflow of the Monte Orgegia Wastewater Treatment Plant (Alicante, Spain) as a demonstrator for energy generation or recuperation at any kind of business processing large amounts of water. The design specifications for the turbine are a flow of 0.37 CMS (m^3/s) and a head of 0.8 m.

As the normal range of Turbulent turbines is from 15 kW up to 70 kW per unit, with a minimal flow of 1.7 CMS and 1.7 m head, the Alicante unit did not fit the micro-hydro category, but it falls into the Pico range of power at 2 kW.

An important element of research in the scope of this project was to reduce and simplify the turbine design for production at pico-scale. This led to a complete redesign of the electronics resulting in a model capable of operating both in on-grid scenarios, off-grid scenarios and cases where grid reliability is a concern and the turbine will guarantee energy availability.

The demonstrator shows that the size reduction of the turbine has an impact on efficiency, yet it can be addressed when redesigning (hydraulically & mechanically) purely for this target size. Most water-treatment sites have stages of treatment where energy recuperation is possible, yet the recuperation capability is often limited. The business case for pico turbines depends on the capability of producing them in high quantities at the same cost / kW as micro turbines (e.g. the current Turbulent product range). This requires a product & business development dedicated to the pico-range.

1 Introduction

Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTP) are among the largest energy consumers in the municipal sector, accounting for approximately 3% of the total electrical energy consumption in developed countries (Longo *et al.* 2016). The energy demand in WWTPs is primarily driven by the following processes:

1. **Pumping:** Wastewater needs to be pumped from its source to the treatment plant and through various stages of the treatment process. Pumping systems can consume a significant portion of the total energy used in a WWTP, ranging from 25% to 40%.
2. **Aeration:** The biological treatment of wastewater, which involves the removal of organic matter and nutrients, requires aeration to supply oxygen to the microorganisms responsible for the treatment process. Aeration systems, such as diffused air systems or mechanical aerators, can account for up to 60% of the total energy consumption in a WWTP.
3. **Sludge Treatment:** The treatment and disposal of sludge, a byproduct of the wastewater treatment process, also requires energy. Processes like sludge thickening, dewatering, and digestion can contribute to the overall energy demand of a WWTP.

Given the substantial energy consumption in WWTPs, there is a growing emphasis on improving energy efficiency and exploring alternative energy sources. Several strategies can be implemented to reduce energy consumption and associated costs:

1. **Process Optimization:** Optimizing the treatment processes through advanced control systems, efficient equipment selection, and operational adjustments can lead to significant energy savings.
2. **Energy Recovery:** WWTPs can recover energy from various sources, such as biogas generated during anaerobic digestion of sludge, which can be used for heating or electricity generation through combined heat and power (CHP) systems.
3. **Renewable Energy Integration:** Incorporating renewable energy sources, such as solar photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, or hydroelectric generators, can offset the energy demand of WWTPs and reduce their carbon footprint.
4. **Energy-Efficient Equipment:** Replacing aging equipment with more energy-efficient alternatives, such as high-efficiency pumps, blowers, and motors, can contribute to substantial energy savings.

The energy consumption in WWTPs is a significant concern due to the energy-intensive nature of the treatment processes and the associated environmental and economic impacts. By implementing energy efficiency measures, optimizing processes, recovering energy from waste streams, and

integrating renewable energy sources, WWTPs can reduce their energy footprint, lower operational costs, and contribute to a more sustainable wastewater management system.

1.1 Case study: Monte Orgegia WWTP

The Monte Orgegia WWTP is one of the two existing treatment plants in the city of Alicante and serves the northern part of the municipality and, partially, the towns of Sant Joan d'Alacant, Mutxamel and El Campello.

The plant is based on a conventional activated sludge process with subsequent anaerobic digestion. It has a combined capacity of 60,000 m³/day thanks to two water treatment lines: one with a capacity of 40,000 m³/day, which corresponds to the extension commissioned in 2006, and a second with a capacity of 20,000 m³/day from the old plant commissioned in 1989.

Figure 1. Aerial view of the Monte Orgegia WWTP

Monte Orgegia also has a sludge line treating through anaerobic digestion the sewage sludge generated both in the primary and secondary settlers. As part of this treatment more than 11 Mm³ of biogas are produced annually, which is used in a cogeneration system to produce heat and electricity for own consumption at the plant. This system significantly reduces the facility's electricity consumption by approximately 35%, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Main figures at Monte Orgegia WWTP (2023 data)

Treated flow rate (m ³ /year)	Electrical consumption (kWh/year)	Cogenerated energy (kWh/year)	Self Sufficiency (%)
11,307,497	4,240,519	1,483,308	35

Alicante LL aims to enhance circular economy strategies within the region, a goal partially realized through the Biofactories initiative promoted by the Veolia Group for various operators across Spain. This initiative is further supported by demonstrating innovative solutions for recovering energy, nutrients, salt, and mineral materials from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), which is the scope of Task 2.1 within WP2.

2 Review of the Current State of Technology in The Market

Microturbines and picoturbines are small turbines that can produce electricity from various fuel sources. In water networks, microturbines can be used to recover energy from the excess pressure in the pipelines, which is typically dissipated through pressure-reducing valves (PRVs). This process is known as micro-hydropower generation or energy recovery in water networks.

The working principle involves installing a microturbine in parallel with a PRV at locations where excess pressure needs to be reduced. The high-pressure water flow is diverted through the microturbine, causing the turbine to spin and generate electricity. The water then exits the microturbine at a lower pressure and continues through the distribution network.

The advantages of using microturbines in water distribution networks are the following:

1. **Energy recovery:** Microturbines allow for the recovery of energy that would otherwise be wasted through PRVs, thereby increasing the overall energy efficiency of the water distribution system.
2. **Renewable energy generation:** The electricity generated by microturbines is considered a renewable energy source, as it is derived from the kinetic energy of the water flow.
3. **Distributed generation:** Microturbines can be installed at multiple locations throughout the water distribution network, providing distributed generation and reducing transmission losses.
4. **Operational cost savings:** The electricity generated by microturbines can be used on-site or fed back into the grid, potentially offsetting energy costs for water utilities.

On the other hand, this technology also offers some challenges and considerations. To start with, identifying suitable locations with sufficient pressure and flow conditions for efficient microturbine operation is crucial. The integration of microturbines into existing water distribution networks may require modifications to the piping and control systems. Microturbines require proper maintenance and monitoring to ensure reliable operation and maximize their lifespan. And finally, the cost-effectiveness of microturbine installations depends on factors such as energy prices, incentives, and the specific site conditions.

Research efforts in this area focus on optimizing microturbine design, improving efficiency, and developing strategies for optimal placement and operation within water distribution networks. Additionally, studies are conducted to assess the economic viability and environmental impact of microturbine installations in various contexts.

According to their functioning principles, the main types of micro and picoturbines include:

1. Turgo Impulse Turbines:

- Turgo turbines are a type of impulse turbine commonly used in micro-hydropower applications, including water distribution networks.
- They are suitable for high head (pressure) and low flow conditions.
- The water jet strikes the turbine runner at an angle, imparting kinetic energy to rotate the runner.
- Turgo turbines are known for their high efficiency and ability to handle a wide range of flow rates.

2. Pelton Wheel Turbines:

- Pelton wheel turbines are another type of impulse turbine suitable for high head and low flow conditions.
- The water jet strikes the double-cup-shaped buckets on the turbine runner, causing it to rotate.
- Pelton wheel turbines are highly efficient and can operate over a wide range of flow rates.
- They are often used in water distribution networks with high pressure differentials.

3. Cross-Flow Turbines:

- Cross-flow turbines, also known as Banki or Michell turbines, are suitable for medium head and flow conditions.
- The water jet strikes the turbine runner twice, once on the outer side and once on the inner side, extracting energy efficiently.
- Cross-flow turbines are relatively simple in design and can handle a wide range of flow rates.
- They are often used in water distribution networks with moderate pressure differentials.

4. Francis Turbines:

- Francis turbines are a type of reaction turbine suitable for medium to high head and flow conditions.
- The water flow is directed radially inward and guided by fixed blades onto the turbine runner.
- Francis turbines are known for their high efficiency and versatility in handling a range of flow rates.
- They are commonly used in larger water distribution networks with higher flow rates.

5. Propeller Turbines:

- Propeller turbines, also known as Kaplan turbines, are suitable for low head and high flow conditions.
- The turbine runner resembles a propeller, with adjustable blades to optimize efficiency for varying flow rates.
- Propeller turbines are often used in water distribution networks with low pressure differentials but high flow rates.

The selection of the appropriate microturbine type depends on factors such as the available head (pressure), flow rate, site conditions, and economic considerations. Proper matching of the turbine characteristics to the specific water distribution network conditions is crucial for optimal energy recovery and efficiency.

The main difference between micro-hydoturbines and pico-hydoturbines is their output power, the generally accepted power ranges are from 5 to 100 kW for micro-hydro and 200 w to 15 kW for pico-hydro. Pico-turbines typically emphasise on extra simplifications, reducing security & regulatory requirements and reducing costs on electric components (e.g. by limiting output to single phase instead of three-phase).

The choice between microturbines and picoturbines depends on factors such as the available water flow and pressure conditions, the desired power output, and the economic feasibility of the installation. In some cases, a combination of both technologies may be employed to optimize energy recovery across different sections of a water distribution network.

When dealing with wastewater networks and treatment plants, the use of this technology faces some limitations, namely:

- **Fouling and corrosion:** Wastewater can contain various contaminants, such as solid particles, grease, and corrosive substances, which can lead to fouling and corrosion of the microturbine components. This may require more frequent maintenance and replacement of parts.
- **Pretreatment requirements:** Depending on the quality of the wastewater, pretreatment processes may be necessary to remove solid particles and other contaminants before the wastewater enters the microturbine. This can add to the overall system complexity and cost.
- **Operational challenges:** The presence of varying flow rates, pressure fluctuations, and potential blockages in wastewater networks can pose operational challenges for microturbines, affecting their efficiency and reliability.
- **Economic feasibility:** The economic viability of microturbine installations in wastewater networks depends on factors such as the available pressure and flow conditions, energy prices, and the costs associated with pretreatment and maintenance.

Most turbine technologies do not fit water plants due to the fact that turbines typically require a pressure difference and/or high heads, which are not available in WWTP. Since the Turbulent technology is an open channel technology and only minimal heads are required (1.5 to 3 m), the technology might be expandable/adaptable to the context of WWTP installations. Turbulent has already successfully installed a turbine at the WWTP installation of Suez at Paris-Versailles. Nevertheless, this installation showed that a specific approach was required. Since the plant cannot be stopped, installation time had to be limited and had to be executed in windows of 6 hours at most, allowing waterflow in between. Further evaluation of multiple WWTP sites shows that in most cases, a turbine (sometimes multiple turbines) of an even smaller size than the actual product range is required for this market. Turbulent produced and installed such turbine to be installed at a WWTP managed by Aguas de Alicante (AMAEM).

3 Technology description at case study

Alicante LL has the ambition of boosting circular economy strategies in the territory, which is articulated partially through the Biofactories initiative fostered by the Veolia Group for a number of operators in the Spanish territory. This approach is being complemented with the demonstration of innovative solutions for recovery of i) energy, ii) nutrients iii) salt and iv) mineral materials, from WWTPs.

In this sense, T2.1. has the objective of recovering energy from wastewater streams by customizing and demonstrating a picoturbine. For achieving this purpose, the case study and the pilot plant approach is drawn in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Energy recovery through picoturbine case-study at Alicante LL

In this sense, a picoturbine demonstrator has been installed serving 2 purposes:

- Evaluate the energy recovery possibilities in WWTPs, based on a real-life installation.
- Developing and investigating a pico-scale turbine and evaluating how it compares to micro-hydro from a technical and commercial perspective.

Based on such a demonstrator, including full installation and operation the parties involved can identify the business value and commercial potential of energy recovery in WWTPs.

For achieving this purpose a turbine installation comprises 3 major components:

- Civil works to embed the turbine in the water flow and provide optimal working conditions for the turbine.
- The turbine impeller at the center of the vortex, excluding gearbox and generator, to convert the energy in the water flow into (typically uncontrolled) electrical energy.
- Gearbox, generator, power electronics and control solution to provide 'well behaved' electrical energy, consistent with grid conditions (in off-grid situations) or coupled to the grid.

These main components are further detailed in the following sections.

3.1 Civil works

The civil works were executed by Aguas De Alicante with the input on dimensions and placement from Turbulent to ensure an optimal installation. The picture depicted in Figure 3 demonstrated a principle design on how to embed the turbine.

Figure 3. Conceptual design of spiral basin and turbine placement into this basin.

Figure 4 shows the as-built civil drawings from Aguas De Alicante. The correct placement of the turbine is critical, both its placement in the vortex/spiral basin as the level at which the turbine is placed plays an essential role for the final performance of the turbine.

Figure 4. Actual civil works design

One of the major advantages of the vortex turbine of Turbulent is the simplification of the civil works in comparison to other hydropower technologies. There is no need for a dam or draft tube, only in certain conditions a weir is required to increase the head to a usable level.

Although smaller, the turbine is very similar to a previous installation at Suez-Versailles by Turbulent, within a concrete rectangular box as part of the outlet structure of the WWTP, the basin structure for the turbine is added. At Suez, all additional structures for the turbine were built in stainless steel (as an assembly) to allow a very quick installation. This was required as the time during which the water flow could be stopped for installation works was limited to 6 hours, eliminating the use of a concrete basin.

Besides scaling down the size of the structures for Aguas De Alicante, the civil works were similar. The dimensions of the basin are 1,738 mm by 1,634 mm (Figure 5).

It must be highlighted that the installation of the turbine was facilitated by simultaneous works in the WWTP to connect the outlet of the two separated secondary treatment lines of the plant, joining them in one single conduit before the tertiary treatment. The connection point between the secondary and tertiary stages turned out to be the optimal point, especially in terms of flow availability, as compared to the inlets and outlets of the plant, in which the stream is divided in several currents.

Figure 5. Design and dimensions of the picoturbine basin

A chamber was built to house the turbine, intercepting the treated water outlet pipe in the shape of a paraboloid in accordance with the manufacturer's technical specifications.

Figure 6. Overview of the WWTP of Monte Orgegia and detail of the aerial image of the turbine.

In the following figures (Figure 7 - 11) the process from the civil works to the picoturbine installation and the final setup is displayed

Figure 7. Excavation at the insertion point of the picoturbine (left), at the outlet of the secondary treatment, and construction of the turbine chamber (right).

Figure 8. Separate construction of the spiral framework for the turbine

Figure 9. Spiral framework in its final position before insertion of the turbine.

Figure 10. Insertion of the turbine in the chamber

Figure 11. Final setup of the picoturbine, with the sluice gate for level control on the right of the image

3.2 Turbine mechanical core

The mechanical part dimensions of the turbine remained similar to the Suez turbine, as the head and flow combination pointed towards a similarly sized and shaped turbine. Turbulent initially considered redesigning the mechanical solution towards other materials and production methodologies, to investigate potential production cost improvements on the pico turbine model but these can only be carried out with production in high quantities and would induce extra costs with minimal further insight in potential future savings within the context of the B-WaterSmart project.

Turbulent did nevertheless re-engineer the machine based on recent experience replacing the production with cast iron (expensive and impractical for very small production quantities) with a simple and cost-effective production process from sheet metal. The impeller is produced in stainless steel, all parts laser-cut out of steel sheets, formed in their final shape and melded into one solid structure. Its design is based on CFD studies and models to create the best matching shape for the head and flow conditions of the site.

The design of the mechanical core as well as its dimensions are depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Detail and dimensions of turbine mechanical part

3.3 Generator and gearbox

On the electrical side, starting with the generator (and gearbox), the turbine was revised completely to match the low-power range below 5 kW. While induction generators are extremely cost-efficient and reliable at high powers in 3-phase operation conditions, the benefits disappear at powers below 7 kW. Turbulent investigated several generator types and brands to select a permanent magnet generator with enough windings to eliminate a gearbox altogether. The nominal rotation speed of the generator is 116 RPM (revolutions per minute).

While Turbulent turbines are typically submersible, with the generator and gearbox integrated into the impeller to make the turbine flood-proof, this setup is unnecessary for WWTPs and submersible machines are too costly for this power range. Therefore, the generator has been mounted above the basin, and the basin has been designed to guarantee sufficient height to eliminate any risk of flooding the generator.

The benefits of these adaptations are:

- lower cost genset (no need for a gearbox).
- lower maintenance costs, by avoiding a gearbox and because the generator is easily accessible.
- a standard motor can be used instead of a 'niche' submersible induction machine.

- The pico-size allows for single phase operation, reducing the complexity on the side of electronics.

3.4 Power electronics

Figure 13 shows the power electronics design in a single line diagram. It is a completely different design from Turbulent standard machines for three main reasons:

- It has been redesigned to save costs for low-power / single-phase designs.
- Electronics for a permanent magnet motor vs induction machine are essentially different.
- It also serves as a concept model of a system that can switch seamlessly between on-grid and off-grid operation.

The core components of the solution are:

- The permanent magnet generator as power source (see above)
- DC/DC MPPT charge controller (+ rectifier between generator and charge controller)
- Battery bank
- Grid-tied inverter having 2 bidirectional AC ports for an on-grid and off-grid side
- Modem/router for remote monitoring

Figure 13. Power electronics design

3.4.1 Operation principle of power-electronics

When there is water flowing through the turbine, the impeller will start rotating. As soon as a sufficiently high rotation speed is reached, the rectified voltage will reach a high enough value for the charge controller to start charging the battery bank (with operating Voltage V_{bat} .)

A minimum of $V_{bat} + 5V$ is required for the charge controller to function correctly, meaning that, at nominal battery voltage, the turbine can charge the batteries at around $38 + 5 = 43V_{dc}$. This corresponds to an AC voltage of $\frac{43}{1,35} = 32,1 V_{ac}$, which in turn corresponds to a turbine velocity of 76 rpm.

The charge controller is parametrized to extract the maximum power available from the turbine. If the battery bank is fully charged, the algorithm will automatically limit the charge current by letting the impeller spin faster (hence, the generator voltage rises). This moves the turbine's point of operation further away from the optimal point, resulting in a lower power extraction.

The grid-tied inverter supplies current to the grid when the battery voltage is within certain limits. In case there is not enough water available and the turbine power output drops, the charge controller will not be able to keep the batteries from discharging to their lower voltage limit. In this case, the inverter will automatically switch off and wait until the battery voltage is in an acceptable range again.

3.4.2 Turbine operational window

The DC/DC charge controller can charge the batteries if its input voltage is between $V_{bat} + 5 = 38 + 5 = 43 V_{dc}$ (at nominal battery voltage) and $150 V_{dc}$. Anywhere outside this window, the batteries cannot be charged. This implies that the impeller's rotational speed must be in the window of 76 - 258 rpm for the electrical system to function properly.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations suggested that the maximum impeller speed at zero load would never be more than $2 * n_{nom} = 2 * 116 rpm = 232 rpm$. Hence the maximum theoretical speed of the turbine is lower than the maximum allowable speed for the charge controller to operate.

Nevertheless, an automatic dump load system was incorporated in the design to ensure optimal reliability and lifetime. When the charge controller's input voltage rises above a preset value, three 10Ω resistors in 'Y' configuration will be directly connected to the generator. This should limit the impeller rotational speed to below 210 rpm in all cases.

This functionality can be switched on manually as well to limit the turbine velocity in case of grid failures or other malfunctions.

3.4.3 Control system functionality

As both the charge controller and grid inverter operate independently and provide an interface for remote monitoring, there is no need to add control functionality to the system. Therefore, a 4G modem and router were added to the system to provide internet access to the charge controller and grid inverter. A 24 V supply powers the router.

4 Demonstration Phase

The civil works were finalized in August 2023 and the demonstration phase started during that month.

The design specifications were based on the flow duration curve obtained at the location where the turbine was to be located and resulted in the turbine model as described in section 3. Figure 14 shows the water flow and the percentage of the time that the flow is higher than or equal to that flow. (e.g. the flow is 100% of the time higher than 0.2 m³/s).

Figure 14. Flow curve vs percentage of time

As you can derive from the graph, for ~94% of the time as measured over a period of 4 years (2018 till 2021), the flow was higher than 0.3 m³/s (370 L/s). Therefore, Turbulent selected this flow as the nominal flow for the turbine, together with a head of 0.8 m, as specified by Aguas de Alicante.

The potential energy was calculated using the formula $0.8 \text{ m (head)} \times 0.37 \text{ m}^3/\text{s (flow)} \times 9.81 \text{ (1 g-force)}$, resulting in 2.9 kW. However, converting 100% of this potential energy is impossible, as it would imply that the water is completely stationary immediately behind the turbine. For systems in the 15 kW to 70 kW range, a realistic water-to-wire efficiency is typically between 60% and 70%. If a similar efficiency could be achieved at the pico scale, the output energy would be approximately 1.9 kW, but typically efficiencies decline at smaller scales.

After installation Turbulent and AMAEM were confronted with a downstream water level that did not correspond to the design specifications and modifying the outlet setup or downstream flow path were not achievable in the scope of the project. As such, the turbine evaluation was performed in two stages:

1. Reliability and continuity of operation from the installation date until the reporting date.

2. Turbine performance evaluation in a short window where the WWTP is partially shutdown in order to briefly match the required downstream water level.

The second evaluation was performed on January 11th 2024, measuring flow, electrical output and water levels. The flow numbers were estimated given that no water flow meter was available directly at the inlet of the turbine. Flow is actually measured and the entrance of the secondary treatment of the plant, but variable retention times, and most importantly, periodic recirculation processes affect the outlet flow. Therefore, this information was used to estimate the water flow at the inlet of the turbine.

4.1 Reliability and continuity

The picture below shows the turbine operation from September 18th 2023 until mid-April 2024. During the first period until December 13th the firmware of the power electronics did not allow injecting energy to the grid once the batteries were fully charged, resulting in a lot of downtime. On December 12th, Turbulent was able to apply custom firmware settings enabling full-time operation of the turbine, after which the turbine has been injecting energy almost full time (see further below).

Figure 15. Power injected in grid over time

The histogram figures below (Figures 16 and 17) demonstrate this further. The histogram in Figure 16 represents the complete period since September 18th, while Figure 17 contains data starting from December 13th. The leftmost block in figure 16 (output power below 120 W) shows that the turbine has been offline for a large amount of time, while in figure 17 this block has largely disappeared.

Figure 16. Power histogram from 09/2023 to 04/2024

Figure 17. Power histogram from 13/12/2023 to mid 04/2024

In figure 18, the relative frequency has been converted in a % of time, demonstrating that the turbine has been running for more than 98.5% of the time after Dec 13th, with the power remaining above 1,040 for more than 82% of the time.

Figure 18. Power histogram from 12/2023 to 04/2024 in relative %.

4.2 Turbine performance

Due to the small available timeframe and limited means for measuring flow and head, the numbers measured and collected required further interpretation. Based on previous detailed turbine modeling, it could be concluded that the picoturbine had a reduced efficiency in comparison to the standard range, which is to be expected as the efficiency of engines and electronics increase with machine size.

Nevertheless, Turbulent is convinced that improvements from the current result could be achieved by sourcing other components and cooperating with partners to adapt their component designs to the specific needs for power generation. This would bring the performance of the pico turbines nearly on-par with the micro-hydro product line.

Table 2 below shows the raw as well as interpreted data of the turbine. An explanation of the interpretation and post-processing steps are explained further down.

Table 2. Raw and treated data of the turbine

	Time	Flow [m ³ /s]	Corrected Flow [m ³ /s]	Net head [cm]	Electrical power [W]	Flow %	Head % M1	Head % M2	Head % (**)	Efficiency [%]	Corrected Efficiency [%]
1 (*)	9:30	0.22	-	42	0	57%	77%	84%	52%	-	-
2 (*)	10:10	0.22	-	36	0	57%	77%	84%	44%	-	-
3	10:35	0.56	0.28	75	555	142%	126%	133%	93%	14%	27%
4 (x)	10:58	0.50	0.47	97	1625	128%	118%	125%	121%	34%	36%
5 (x)	11:30	0.44	0.45	95	1405	114%	110%	117%	118%	34%	33%
6 (x)	12:00	0.42	0.44	93	1113	107%	106%	113%	116%	29%	28%
7 (x)	12:10	0.47	0.48	98	1575	121%	114%	121%	122%	35%	34%
8 (x)	12:20	0.42	0.39	87	1597	107%	106%	113%	109%	45%	48%
9	12:40	0.44	0.24	70	821	114%	110%	117%	88%	27%	49%
10	12:50	0.44	0.32	79	1139	114%	110%	117%	99%	33%	46%
11	13:00	0.44	0.25	71	897	114%	110%	117%	89%	29%	51%

Without interpretation and postprocessing, there seems to be a high variability in the head versus flow relation e.g. item 5,9-11 suggest a variation of head of more than 30% with the exact same flow. Previous extensive CFD and live studies at Turbulent have proven that there is a very clear and linear relationship between head and flow (at a fixed turbine rotation speed). The graph below shows a head in function of flow curve for one of our turbine models on which the Alicante pico turbine is based:

Figure 19. Head vs flow curve in % of their nominal values

Note that head and the flow are represented as the relative head and flow in comparison to their nominal values to simplify comparison between different models. The graph proves the linear correlation between both values which is also expected from a theoretical basis (on condition the turbine speed remains identical).

As this curve is representative for a turbine with impeller diameter of 130 cm, a different curve is expected for the 80 cm impeller for the picoturbine, but still a linear relationship.

Figure 20 shows the exact same curve (blue) and an adapted one (yellow), superimposed on the measurement data.

Figure 20. comparison of theoretical curve with Alicante measurements.

The green dots show the head measured values while the blue dots (Head%M1) represent the expected head % values when applying the formula shown in figure 19 [head% = 0.5675 flow% + 0.4503.] The red dots and line (Head % M2) provide a correction on that formula to correspond to the measured values in the 100% to 130% range. Since measuring the head in the turbine is an effective way of determining the flow through the machine, the above formula was used to correct some flow values that were unrealistic.

Notes:

- The first 2 measurements are ignored as the measured head and flow do not correspond at all with the energy output: the energy output (> 1350 W) suggest much higher values for both parameters. Turbulent assumes that at the start of the process, some measurements have been done incorrectly so they are ignored.

The resulting peak performance of the pico turbine is in the range of 48-51%, quite a lot lower than our standard turbines. Several factors cause this lower efficiency:

- The small size of the machine, knowing that several parameters affecting hydraulic efficiency do not scale down linearly with size. (e.g. the surface % where water can flow freely through the turbine is higher as the turbine size decreases.)

- Several mechanical and electrical losses do not scale linearly either. (Losses in gearbox & bearings, losses due to the gap between impeller and shroud.)

Nevertheless, further developments specifically targeting pico turbines and the production of them in high quantities can resolve several of the challenges posed in a 1-off installation. As such, Turbulent is convinced that achieving a 55-60% efficiency is obtainable.

5 Impact, Market and Conditions

Although the energy recovery in this demonstrator is neglectable, as a proof of concept, the project proves we have a market for energy recovery at large and very large WWTP's (> 500,000 inhabitants) with a pico/micro-hydro plant of at least 10 kW.

The environmental impact of a vortex turbine is best-in-class of all renewable energy sources. A comparison based on data from Rensmart (<https://www.rensmart.com/HomePage>) shows that a micro-hydro installation strongly outperforms solar and wind in CO₂ reduction/€ invested when compared over a lifetime of 30 years. This is illustrated in Table 3, which compares CO₂ savings across the three renewable energies.

Table 3. CO₂ savings comparison with solar and wind energy

Technology	Avg. cost/kW	PF	Avg kWh/y	CO ₂ Reduction Category	kg CO ₂ /kWh	CO ₂ Ton /10Y	CO ₂ Ton in 30 y	CO ₂ kg / €	€/Ton CO ₂
Solar	1,700	24.5%	2,146	On-grid Solar	0.25	5.39	16	10	105.19
Wind	3,000	34.8%	3,048	On-grid Wind	0.30	9.28	28	9	107.78
Turbulent	4,000	85.0%	7,446	On-grid	0.30	22.64	68	17	58.90

Figure 21. CO₂ savings comparison with solar and wind

This superior environmental impact achieved with turbines can be attributed to several factors:

- **Higher plant factor:** Hydro installations operate more consistently compared to solar or wind, leading to greater energy output relative to capacity.
- **Lower environmental footprint:** Minimal use of rare earth materials during production and high recyclability contribute to the low environmental impact, both during production and decommissioning.
- **Lower operational costs and extended lifetime:** Hydro installations require less maintenance and have a longer operational lifetime.

Furthermore, the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) for these installations can be as low as 0.06 €/kWh, with most turbulent hydro projects falling between 0.04 and 0.06 €/kWh. For the WWTP segment, which falls into the lower power range of turbines, the LCOE is typically at the higher end of this range.

A simplified LCOE calculation is shown in the table below for an on-grid 15 kW turbine, running with a plant factor of 85%. All numbers used are indicative only as they can strongly vary on a case-by-case basis. The calculation does not assume an economy-of-scale, but a fully standardized turbine requiring no engineering nor customizations to the core turbine; only engineering related to the placement and integration of the turbine in the WWTP.

Table 4. LCOE estimation with simplified model

Parameter	Value	Unit
Capex	120,000	€
Opex	2,400	€/year
Turbine power	15	kW
Plant factor	85	%
Energy	111,690	kWh/year
Lifetime	30	Year
Lifetime cost	192,000	€
Lifetime energy	3,350,700	kWh
Estimated LCOE	0.06	€/kWh

In succession to the Suez and Alicante installations, Turbulent has been contacted by an installer in Phoenix (Arizona, USA) for projects in multiple large WWTP sites. Similarly, there is a very high interest from a Scottish WWTP operator to equip their large sites with vortex turbines. All these sites have a flow above 1.5 CMS (m^3/s) for 90% of the time. One of the Scottish sites for which a detailed LCOE calculation has been performed, the resulting LCOE is 0.062 €/kWh in accordance with the table above. In the case of Alicante, the biggest WWTP (i.e. Rincón de León) has an average flow rate of 0.4 CMS and the biggest one in the Valencian Community (i.e. Pinedo WWTP) has 1.4 CMS of flow rate.

In the overall renewable energy market, it can be concluded that whenever the conditions are suitable for installing a micro-hydro-, and more specific a vortex-turbine, it outperforms other renewable energy sources in terms of both economic and ecological benefits (on condition that the turbine is fish-friendly.)

In the context of the WWTP market, where low-flow conditions limit power generation capacity, favorable surrounding conditions are required. In addition, the market should not be addressed on a site-by-site basis. Instead, collaborating with partners or operators managing multiple sites will leverage economies of scale, making the investment more feasible and impactful. Recent experiences demonstrate this approach to be feasible and effective.

5.1 Required conditions for energy recovery at WWTP sites

For successful energy recovery in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), several key conditions must be met:

1. **Flow and head availability:** As with any turbine installation, the available flow and head are critical. A general guideline is that the product of head (in meters) and flow (in cubic meters per second, CMS) should be greater than 1.5 to ensure efficient energy recovery. This condition is equivalent to a lower threshold of **1 million inhabitants** equivalent for the treatment volume of WWTPs.
2. **Optimal installation site selection:**
 - a. Ensure the hydraulic parameters, such as flow rate and head, meet the turbine's operating requirements.
 - b. Confirm adequate space is available for both the turbine chamber and the control cabinet.
 - c. Verify proximity to existing electrical and data connections for remote control and monitoring systems.
3. **Flow variability:**
 - a. Account for the irregular seasonal and daily flow patterns common in WWTPs, which differ significantly from the more stable conditions typically found in rivers and channels, where microturbines are usually deployed.
 - b. Implement automated upstream level control systems to manage flow variability and maintain consistent turbine operation.
4. **Installation and maintenance considerations:**
 - a. Ensure there is the potential for water flow detention or diversion to facilitate both installation and maintenance activities.
 - b. Favorable civil works conditions are crucial to minimize construction complexity and costs.
5. **Economy of scale:** Consider leveraging economies of scale by planning installations across multiple sites simultaneously to reduce overall costs and increase project efficiency.

6 Conclusion

As mentioned previously, the picoturbine has worked continuously since its installation, almost one year prior to the production of this report. Energy injection to the grid has had no interruptions after the firmware update in December 12th 2023.

Qualitatively, all the expected benefits of this innovative technology in relation to usual solutions the recovery of hydraulic energy in water networks have been fulfilled:

- No need for pressurized conduits; the turbine is perfectly fit for open channel flow, frequent in WWTPs.
- Robustness and low maintenance, according to the experience so far. Open channel installation eases supervision and future maintenance.
- Resistance to the presence of debris and aggressive water (high conductivity, low pH)
- Extremely low head conditions of functioning (< 1m)

It must also be highlighted that the detailed instructions provided by Turbulent allowed the accurate independent development of the civil works by the final user (AMAEM). The correct implementation of this preliminary phase meant that the installation and commissioning of the turbine itself required only a few hours.

On the other hand, the low output of the installed picoturbine for the available head and flow actually means that **the implementation of this solution in WWTPs should be considered only for large and very large plants of a Population equivalent (PE) above 500,000 inhabitants**. In a case such as the present one (Monte Orgegia WWTP - PE 200,000 inh.) the investment return hardly justifies the adoption of this technology, especially when compared with options such as cogeneration of biogas or even conventional photovoltaic panels. In our case, the simultaneous development of other hydraulic works in the plant reduced the cost of civil works to achieve an economically sustainable investment.

In conclusion, the integration of pico/micro-hydro plants for energy recovery at large and very large WWTPs presents a promising solution for enhancing sustainability in wastewater treatment. While the energy recovery in the current demonstrator is minimal, the project successfully proves the feasibility of such installations, particularly in facilities serving populations above 500,000. Vortex turbines, with their high plant factor, low environmental footprint, and superior CO₂ reduction per euro invested, outperform both solar and wind energy technologies over a 30-year lifespan. However, to achieve optimal performance, careful attention must be paid to the hydraulic parameters, site selection, flow variability, and installation logistics. Addressing these factors and leveraging economies of scale can make the widespread deployment of micro-hydro plants at WWTPs both economically and environmentally viable. This innovative approach not only reduces greenhouse gas emissions but also aligns with circular economy principles by recovering energy from existing wastewater streams.

References

Mérida García, A., Rodríguez Díaz, J. A., García Morillo, J., & McNabola, A. (2021). Energy recovery potential in industrial and municipal wastewater networks using micro-hydropower in Spain. *Water*, 13(5), 691.

Punys, P., & Radzevičius, A. Integrating microturbines into sewage systems of lowland areas. In *XII Polska Konferencja Hydroenergetyczna XIIth Polish Hydropower Conference* (p. 73).

Rodríguez-Pérez, Á. M., & Pulido-Calvo, I. (2019). Analysis and viability of microturbines in hydraulic networks: a case study. *Journal of Water Supply: Research and Technology—AQUA*, 68(6), 474-482.

Soares, R. B., Memelli, M. S., Roque, R. P., & Gonçalves, R. F. (2017). Comparative analysis of the energy consumption of different wastewater treatment plants. *International Journal of Architecture, Arts and Applications*, 3(6), 79-86.

Svardal, K., & Kroiss, H. (2011). Energy requirements for waste water treatment. *Water Science and Technology*, 64(6), 1355-1361.

Yaakob, O. B., Ahmed, Y. M., Elbatran, A. H., & Shabara, H. M. (2014). A review on micro hydro gravitational vortex power and turbine systems. *Jurnal teknologi*, 69(7), 1-7.

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